

Microplastics and Human Health Consortium

MOMENTUM and MORE MOMENTUM

Deliverable Report

D3.3 Report on in vitro dosimetry model and its applicability for the MOMENTUM MNPs

WP3 MNP biokinetics

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Description:

Task 3.3: Obtaining parameters for dosimetry modelling.

Dosimetry of the MNP in the in vitro models used is a key aspect for the interpretation of the results. This not only holds true for the work in WP3, but also for the WP4A experiments, and the extrapolation towards use of data in risk assessment (WP6). Several in silico approaches (tools) are available (i.e. In vitro Sedimentation, Diffusion and Dosimetry (ISDD), DosiGUI). These in silico tools require specific parameters that are either media or MNP specific. Cell culture media parameters that are required include viscosity, density and refractive index of media. The following MNP parameters are required: hydrodynamic sizes for the smaller size fractions assessed via DLS (which is only possible for the smaller-sized MNPs: available at RIVM, UT, WU-TOX, OU. A limited number of samples can be analysed by SLS (OU), if required); primary particle size distribution (SEM characterisation is part of the MNP passports (WP1); and, effective density of MNP and its agglomerates (obtained by Volumetric Centrifugation Density: available at WU-TOX). Part of this data will be provided by WP1 (MNP passports), while others will be obtained by WP3 partners as indicated.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Given the vast diversity and dynamic properties of micro- and nano-plastics (MNPs), relying solely on animal studies for assessing their potential health risks is impractical¹⁻³. Instead, *in vitro* cell assays have become the preferred method for assessing the potential perturbations of physiological processes, providing rapid and efficient screening of the potential effects of MNPs¹⁻³. However, for the accurate interpretation and comparison of the results from different *in vitro* experiments and for a valid extrapolation to *in vivo* observations, dosimetry of MNPs must be considered^{3, 4}.

Dosimetry in the context of MNPs refers to the determination and quantification of the concentration of particles that cells are exposed to during experiments (i.e. the fraction of MNP deposited on the cells versus the nominal concentration of MNPs added to the *in vitro* test system)⁴. Unlike soluble compounds, where the concentration of a drug or chemical administered to the culture medium is generally uniform and readily available to the cells, MNPs have unique behavior including sedimentation, agglomeration, and buoyancy, all of which can substantially alter the actual concentration or amount of MNPs that reaches the cells⁵. For example, buoyant MNPs may remain suspended at the surface of the culture medium and fail to reach cells anchored at the bottom of an *in vitro* test system, potentially leading to an underestimation of their toxic effects and drawing misleading conclusions regarding their safety.

The concentration (in mass or number) of particles delivered to cells can be predicted using mathematical models that incorporate both the physicochemical properties of the particles and the specific conditions of the *in vitro* exposure scenario. Among the available computational tools, three notable models include the *In vitro* Sedimentation, Diffusion and Dosimetry model (ISDD)⁶, the *In vitro* Sedimentation, Diffusion, Dissolution and Dosimetry model (ISD3)⁷, and the Distorted Grid model (DG)⁴. Each of these models offers unique features tailored to different aspects of particle behavior and experimental setups.

The ISDD model focuses on sedimentation and diffusion, key factors in determining how particles behave in a static culture medium⁶. This model is particularly useful for scenarios where these physical processes predominantly influence particle interactions with cells⁶. It calculates how particles settle and diffuse over time, providing a baseline understanding of their behavior under static conditions⁶.

Advancing from ISDD, the ISD3 model incorporates an additional parameter: dissolution⁷. This enhancement makes ISD3 suitable for experiments involving soluble or partially soluble materials⁷. By accounting for dissolution, ISD3 can better predict the bioavailability and toxicity of particles that undergo significant chemical transformations *in vitro*, providing a more comprehensive analysis of their potential impacts⁷.

For more complex scenarios involving a range of particle sizes, types, and behaviors, the DG model offers a sophisticated approach⁴. The DG model incorporates not just sedimentation, diffusion, and dissolution but also adsorption and polydispersity⁴, where it is noted that for MNPs dissolution does not need to be considered. It uses a Langmuir isotherm to simulate biokinetics at the particle-cell interface, making it highly effective for studies involving diverse MNPs with complex interactions in biological media⁴.

In the present report, DG model was selected for the prediction of the sedimentation of a panel of Momentum MNPs due to its enhanced capabilities in handling the complex dynamics of MNPs.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium/Nutrient Mixture F-12 (DMEM/F12) cell culture medium without phenol red was purchased from Gibco (Paisley, UK). mTeSR™ Plus medium for human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs) was purchased from Stem Cell Technologies (Vancouver, Canada). Fetal bovine serum (FBS) was purchased from Invitrogen (Breda, The Netherlands). Deionized water (dH₂O) was prepared by a Milli-Q system (Millipore, MA, USA).

2.2 MNPs

The MNPs used in this study were provided by TNO (see DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13683074.).

Table 1 MNPs used in this study with the respective abbreviations.

Particles	Abbreviations
Polypropylene, < 1 μm	PP<1
Polypropylene, 1-5 μm	PP1-5
Polypropylene, 5-10 μm	PP5-10
Polypropylene, 90-150 μm	PP90-150
Polyamide, < 1 μm	PA<1
Polyamide, 1-5 μm	PA1-5
Polyamide, 5-10 μm	PA5-10
Polyamide, > 100 μm	PA>100
Polyvinyl chloride, < 1 μm	PVC<1
Polyvinyl chloride, 1-5 μm	PVC1-5
Polyvinyl chloride, 5-10 μm	PVC5-10
Polyvinyl chloride, 90-150 μm	PVC90-150

2.3 Measurement of medium density and viscosity

Two types of cell culture medium were used in this study: DMEM/F12 medium supplemented with 10% FBS, and human induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSCs) culture medium supplemented with 2% FBS.

Medium density was assessed by equilibrating 1.5 ml Eppendorf tubes, deionized water (dH₂O), and each medium to 37°C. Density was determined by pipetting 1000 μl samples into tared tubes and recording the weight. The density of the media was calculated using the formula: $\rho_{\text{medium}} = \rho_{\text{lit. H}_2\text{O}} \times \rho_{\text{measured medium}} / \rho_{\text{measured H}_2\text{O}}$, with the density of dH₂O at 37°C (0.9933 g/cm³) obtained from literature was used for calibration. This measurement was repeated five times for accuracy.

Viscosity was measured using a Ubbelohde-type viscometer (Nr. 501 01/0a, Schott Geräte GmbH, Germany), equilibrated along with the media to 37°C. The viscometer was filled, and the flow time from the upper to the lower mark was timed with a stopwatch. The viscosity of each medium was calculated using the formula: $\text{Viscosity}_{\text{medium}} = \text{Viscosity}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \times \rho_{\text{medium}} \times t_{\text{medium}} / \rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \times t_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, where $\text{Viscosity}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 0.6913 \text{ mPa}\cdot\text{s}$ and $\text{Density}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 0.9933 \text{ g/cm}^3$ at 37°C. The viscometer was thoroughly

cleaned with water, isopropanol, and acetone between different medium measurements to prevent cross-contamination and ensure accuracy. This measurement was performed three times.

2.4 Determination of effective densities of MNPs

The effective density of MNPs was quantified using a centrifugation method. MNPs were suspended at a concentration of 250 µg/ml in DMEM/F12 and iPSC medium, and 2 ml of this suspension was dispensed into each well of 6-well plates. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours (a duration typical of in vitro cell-based studies). After incubation, 1 ml of each suspension was transferred to pre-weighed PCV tubes (Westburg, Leusden, The Netherlands). The tubes were centrifuged at 2000g for 1 hour. The volume of the resultant particle pellet (V_{pellet}) was measured using an Easy-read volume measurement device (Westburg, Leusden, The Netherlands). This procedure was replicated three times, with two technical replicates each, to ensure consistency.

Effective densities (ρ_{EV}) were calculated using the formula:

$$\rho_{\text{EV}} = \rho_{\text{medium}} + \left[\left(\frac{M_{\text{ENM}}}{V_{\text{pellet}} \cdot \text{SF}} \right) \left(1 - \frac{\rho_{\text{medium}}}{\rho_{\text{ENM}}} \right) \right].$$

In this equation, ρ_{medium} represents the density of the medium, which was quantified as described in Section 2.3; M_{ENM} is the mass of MNPs, with a value of 0.00025g used; SF refers to the packing factor, with a value of 0.635 used for random stacking particles (e.g., heterogeneous particles produced by milling); ρ_{ENM} denotes the initial density of the particles, which was sourced from literature.

2.5 Static Light Scattering (SLS) analysis

The Static Light Scattering (SLS) analysis of the hydrodynamic size distribution of MNPs were performed using Malvern Mastersizer 3000 equipped with Hydro SV, a small volume wet sample dispersion unit (Malvern Instruments Ltd., Malvern, UK). MNPs were suspended at a concentration of 100 µg/ml in DMEM/F12 medium supplemented with 10% FBS and incubated at 37°C for approximately 6h prior to the analysis. Each sample was then shortly vortexed (5 sec) and 1 ml was added to the SLS measuring cell containing approx. 6 mL of DMEM/F12 medium with 10% FBS. Measurements were performed at room temp., under constant agitation using a magnetic stirrer set at 600 rpm. This constant movement minimizes particle sedimentation and ensures a homogenous dispersion throughout the measurements. For calculating the particle size distributions, specific refractive and absorption indices were applied based on the material properties of each MNP type i.e., PVC (1.54, 0.01i), PP (1.49, 0.01i), PA (1.53, 0.01i). Refractive index of the dispersant was set at 1.33. Measurements were performed using non-spherical particle mode and data processing using a general-purpose analysis model integrated within the Mastersizer software. Data is presented as an average of 3 consecutive measurements per sample.

2.6 Particle sedimentation modeling with DG model

We used the DG model to simulate the sedimentation behavior of Momentum particles. The DG model was implemented using a standalone version that operates with both Dosigui and Riskgone

frameworks and was run using MATLAB (the script can be found in the supplementary file). The parameter settings are as follows:

The volume column height, representing the distance from the assumed cell layer to the medium surface, was set at two different values to accommodate different experimental setups. The height was set to, 3 mm, approximating the volume conditions used in typical well plates, including 96-well (100 μ l), 48-well (330 μ l), 24-well (500 μ l), 12-well (1 ml), and 6-well (2.75 ml) plates, and to 6.6 mm for the Transwell insert system, which corresponds to a volume of 0.4 ml in a 0.6 cm² insert. These configurations help capture the varying exposure conditions across different plate formats.

The DG model was configured with the assumption that particles reaching the cell layer were considered bound, corresponding to having the “sticky bottom” setting on. The adsorption dissociation constant was set to the empirical value of 10^{-9} , consistent with non-specific binding behavior. When combined with the 'sticky bottom' setting, this low dissociation constant ensures that most particles remain attached to the cell layer, minimizing their release back into the medium and thus maximizing cell exposure.

The density and viscosity values of the medium used were those of DMEM with 10% FBS, as described in Section 2.3, measured at a temperature of 37°C, which was also set as the solvent temperature in the DG model to ensure consistency with the experimental conditions. Effective densities of the MNPs were calculated as described in Section 2.4, using DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS and iPSC medium supplemented with 2% FBS. The hydrodynamic size distribution of the MNPs used in the model was obtained via SLS also in DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS.

The initial concentration of MNPs used for model predictions was set at 0.125 mg/ml. This concentration reflects a realistic exposure level commonly used in in vitro toxicological studies. The DG model incorporates the medium's physicochemical properties, including density and viscosity, as well as the characteristics of MNPs including hydrodynamic size and adsorption properties, to provide a detailed prediction of the delivered concentration to cells.

In addition, for the iPSC medium, we only conducted sedimentation modeling for PVC particles and assumed that the hydrodynamic size of the particles in iPSC medium was the same as in DMEM, as we did not perform SLS measurements in the iPSC medium.

2.7 Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis was conducted to assess the impact of key model parameters on particle sedimentation predictions. Specifically, we adjusted the hydrodynamic size, adsorption dissociation constant, medium density, medium viscosity and effective density of the MNPs by increasing each parameter by 10%, while keeping the other parameters constant, to evaluate their individual effects on the model outcomes. For this analysis, only PP particles were selected as it is expected that for all MNPs the same parameters would be influential.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Medium density and viscosity

The medium viscosity was determined to be 0.7031 mPa·s for DMEM with 10% serum and 0.7078 mPa·s for iPSCs medium with 2% serum. The medium density was measured as 0.9987 g/cm³ for DMEM with 10% serum and 0.9971 g/cm³ for iPSCs medium with 2% serum. These values are comparable between the two media.

3.2 Effective density

The effective densities of the MNPs were calculated for different media conditions, as shown in Table 2. The measurements revealed that effective densities varied depending on the type of medium used, particle size, and particle type. For DMEM with 10% FBS, effective densities ranged from 1.03 to 1.20 g/cm³, while for iPSCs medium with 2% FBS, effective densities varied more significantly, ranging from 1.03 to 1.39 g/cm³.

It was observed that the medium type had a more pronounced effect on the effective density of larger particles, particularly for PVC and PA particles. For example, the effective density of PVC (90-150 nm) was 1.39 g/cm³ in the iPSCs medium, compared to 1.20 g/cm³ in the DMEM medium. Similarly, PA (>100 nm) showed a significant difference in effective density between the two media, indicating that the medium composition influences the behavior of larger particles more significantly than smaller ones.

Table 2 Initial material densities and calculated effective densities of MNPs.

MNPs	Initial density (g/cm ³)	DMEM (10% FBS)		iPSCs medium (2% FBS)	
		V pellet (μL)	Effective density (g/cm ³)	V pellet (μL)	Effective density (g/cm ³)
PP<1	1.68	1.34	1.12	1.11	1.14
PP1-5	1.39	1.31	1.08	Not available ^a	/ ^c
PP5-10	1.39	2.30	1.05	Not available ^a	/ ^c
PP 90-150	1.68	1.07	1.15	1.05	1.15
PA<1	1.14	1.41	1.03	1.58	1.03
PA1-5	1.14	1.68	1.03	1.10	1.04
PA5-10	1.14	1.30	1.04	1.08	1.04
PA>100	1.14	0.57	1.08	0.24	1.20
PVC<1	1.38	Not available ^a	1.08 (assumed) ^b	Not available ^a	1.10 (assumed) ^b
PVC1-5	1.38	1.31	1.08	1.03	1.10
PVC5-10	1.38	1.29	1.08	1.12	1.09
PVC 90-150	1.38	0.54	1.20	0.28	1.39

^a Not enough material

^b The value of the larger fraction was used.

^c could not be calculated as V pellet was missing

3.3 Hydrodynamic sizes of MNPs by SLS

The hydrodynamic sizes of MNPs were measured by Static Light Scattering (SLS) in DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS, as shown in Figure 1. The results indicate that PP<1 and PP1-5 have similar size distributions, while PP5-10 has a larger average size compared to both. For PA particles, PA5-10 shows a smaller average SLS size than PA1-5. In the case of PVC particles, all three sizes (PVC<1, PVC1-5, and PVC5-10) show similar size distributions, with minimal differences.

Figure 1. Hydrodynamic size distribution of MNPs measured by SLS in DMEM with 10% FBS

3.4 Predicted sedimentation

The predicted sedimentation behavior of different particles was modeled under two different volume column heights: 3 mm and 6.6 mm, as summarized in Table 3 and illustrated in Figures 2 and 3. Figure 2 represents the results for a 3 mm column height, while Figure 3 shows results for a 6.6 mm column height. The sedimentation patterns of particles of various types and sizes were compared across both conditions.

The sedimentation rate varied significantly between different particle types of the same size. For example, PP<1, PA1-5, and PVC<1 showed distinct sedimentation behaviors. PVC<1 particles reached near-complete deposition (95.6% for both 3 mm and 6.6 mm column heights) within 24 hours (T_{max} of 10.5 and 22.0 hours, respectively). In contrast, PA1-5 had a higher fraction deposited (86.8% for both heights) compared to PP<1, which exhibited slower and less complete sedimentation, with the fraction deposited reaching 42.3% and 37.4% after 48 hours in the 3 mm and 6.6 mm conditions, respectively.

For the same type of particle, size had a significant influence on sedimentation. In both Figures 2 and 3, PP and PA particles showed faster sedimentation as their size increased. Larger particles generally settled faster due to higher sedimentation forces acting on them, which is consistent across both column heights. For example, PP5-10 had a T_{max} of 10.5 hours at 3 mm and 20.5 hours at 6.6 mm,

with $f_{D \max}$ values of 96.5% for both heights, indicating more efficient sedimentation compared to smaller PP particles.

The volume column height also had a noticeable impact on sedimentation rates. For smaller particles, such as PP<1, the fraction of sedimented particles was slightly lower at the 6.6 mm volume height compared to the 3 mm height, suggesting that increasing the column height results in more dispersion and less complete sedimentation. Larger particles, such as PP5-10, were less influenced by column height, with similar deposition percentages in both 3 mm and 6.6 mm conditions. This indicates that the effect of volume column height is more pronounced for smaller particles, likely due to their lower mass and greater susceptibility to Brownian motion.

In terms of AUC (area under the curve), which represents the cumulative sedimentation over time, PVC particles showed slightly higher AUC values for the 3 mm column compared to the 6.6 mm column, indicating more rapid and comprehensive sedimentation in the shorter column height. For PA and PP particles, the AUC values also reflected the trends seen in T_{\max} and $f_{D \max}$, with larger particles generally achieving higher AUC values, suggesting more effective sedimentation. Smaller particles like PP<1 had lower AUC values at 6.6 mm compared to 3 mm, highlighting the impact of column height on their dispersion and sedimentation efficiency.

These results demonstrate that both particle size and volume column height are crucial parameters in determining the sedimentation behavior of MNPs. Larger particles tend to settle more rapidly and completely, whereas smaller particles show more variability depending on the height of the medium column.

Additionally, we performed sedimentation modeling exclusively for PVC particles in iPSC medium supplemented with 2% FBS (Table S1 and Figures S1 and S2). When comparing these results to the DMEM medium supplemented with 10% FBS (Table 3), PVC particles in iPSC medium displayed slightly faster sedimentation across both 3 mm and 6.6 mm column heights. This is evidenced by lower T_{\max} values for iPSC medium, such as PVC<1 with T_{\max} of 9.0 hours for the 3 mm column height, compared to 10.5 hours in DMEM. Similarly, the AUC values in iPSC medium were slightly higher for the 3 mm column height, indicating more efficient sedimentation in the iPSC medium compared to DMEM. These findings suggest that the composition of the medium can influence the sedimentation dynamics, potentially due to differences in medium properties like viscosity or protein content.

Table 3 Predicted sedimentation metrics for different MNPs at 3 mm and 6.6 mm column heights (DMEM with 10%FBS)

MNPs	T_{\max} (h)		$f_{D \max}$ (%)		AUC (%*h)	
	3 mm	6.6 mm	3 mm	6.6 mm	3 mm	6.6 mm
PP<1	> 48	> 48	42.3	37.4	1649.4	1238.6
PP1-5	> 48	> 48	45.5	39.7	1735.6	1255.9
PP5-10	10.5	20.5	96.5	96.5	4537.4	4401.2
PA1-5	38.5	> 48	86.8	86.8	3871.2	3487.1
PA5-10	> 48	> 48	73.4	71.2	3107.6	2657.6
PVC<1	10.5	22.0	95.6	95.6	4495.5	4356.3

PVC1-5	8.0	16.5	96.8	96.7	4571.5	4458.2
PVC5-10	8.5	18.0	96.5	96.5	4553.2	4434.3

Figure 2. Predicted sedimentation in volume column height of 3 mm (DMEM with 10%FBS).

PA<1 No SLS data available

Legend: Y-axis: fraction deposited (%); X-axis time in hours (48 hours)

Figure 3. Predicted sedimentation in volume column height of 6.6 mm (DMEM with 10%FBS).

PA<1 No SLS data available

Legend: Y-axis: fraction deposited (%); X-axis time in hours (48 hours)

3.5 Sensitivity analysis

The sensitivity analysis was conducted to understand the impact of increasing different parameters by 10% on the predicted sedimentation of PP particles in DMEM with 10% FBS at a volume column height of 3 mm. Table 4 summarizes the effects of increasing hydrodynamic size, adsorption dissociation constant, medium density, medium viscosity, and effective density on T_{max} , $f_{D\ max}$, and AUC values. Figures 4 to 8 correspond to the sensitivity analyses of each parameter respectively

It was observed that increasing the hydrodynamic size led to a significant increase in sedimentation efficiency for all PP particles. For instance, PP5-10 showed a reduction in T_{max} , from 10.5 hours to 9.0 hours, with an increase in $f_{D\ max}$ from 96.5% to 97.3%, and an AUC increase from 4537.4%*h to 4595.6%*h (Tables 3 and 4), indicating faster and more complete sedimentation.

Increasing the effective density also led to enhanced sedimentation. PP5-10 experienced a decrease in T_{max} from 10.5 hours to 3.5 hours, while $f_{D\ max}$ increased to 98.8%, and AUC rose to 4671.6%*h (Tables 3 and 4), highlighting that higher effective density promotes faster sedimentation. In contrast, increasing the adsorption dissociation constant had no observable effect on sedimentation behavior for PP particles. For PP5-10, T_{max} , $f_{D\ max}$, and AUC values remained unchanged compared to

the original conditions (Tables 3 and 4), suggesting that adsorption at the cell layer did not limit particle movement under the given conditions.

When analyzing the effect of increasing medium density, smaller particles like PP<1 showed reduced sedimentation, with a decrease in T_{\max} to 13.2% and AUC to 471.9%*h (Tables 3 and 4). However, for larger particles (PP1-5 and PP5-10), increasing the medium density to values greater than the particle's effective density led to no sedimentation, making the particles buoyant.

Increasing the medium viscosity also affected sedimentation rates, especially for PP5-10, which experienced an increase in T_{\max} to 11.5 hours, while $f_{D \max}$ and AUC values remained similar to the original conditions, suggesting that higher viscosity slows down the sedimentation process.

These findings indicate that hydrodynamic size, effective density, medium density, and viscosity are key parameters influencing sedimentation. Hydrodynamic size and effective density particularly enhance sedimentation, while higher medium density and viscosity generally hinder it. The adsorption dissociation constant appears to have minimal impact under the given condition.

Table 4 Sensitivity analysis of the impact of different parameters on predicted T_{\max} , $f_{D \max}$, and AUC for PP particles in a 3 mm volume column height (DMEM with 10% FBS)

MNPs	Parameters that were modified in the analysis	T_{\max} (h)	$f_{D \max}$ (%)	AUC (%*h)
PP<1	hydrodynamic size	> 48	48.1	1923.1
PP1-5		> 48	51.7	2034.5
PP5-10		9.0	97.3	4595.6
PP<1	adsorption dissociation constant	> 48	42.3	1649.4
PP1-5		> 48	45.5	1735.5
PP5-10		10.5	96.5	4537.4
PP<1	medium density	> 48	13.2	471.9
PP1-5		> 48	0	0
PP5-10		> 48	0	0
PP<1	medium viscosity	> 48	42.1	1611.0
PP1-5		> 48	45.3	1667.5
PP5-10		11.5	96.5	4526.2
PP<1	effective density	> 48	55.7	2377.6
PP1-5		45	63.5	2716.3
PP5-10		3.5	98.8	4671.6

Figure 4. Predicted sedimentation with 10% increase in SLS size of PPs while keeping other parameters unchanged, using volume height of 3 mm (DMEM with 10%FBS).

Figure 5. Predicted sedimentation with 10% increase in adsorption dissociation constant of PPs while keeping other parameters unchanged, using volume height of 3 mm(DMEM with 10% FBS).

Figure 6. Predicted sedimentation with 10% increase in medium density of PPs while keeping other parameters unchanged, using volume height of 3 mm (DMEM with 10%FBS).

Figure 7. Predicted sedimentation with 10% increase in medium viscosity of PPs while keeping other parameters unchanged, using volume height of 3 mm.

Figure 8. Predicted sedimentation with 10% increase in effective density of PPs while keeping other parameters unchanged, using volume height of 3 mm.

4 CONCLUSION

- The study predicted the sedimentation behavior of different MNPs under two volume column heights (3 mm and 6.6 mm) using the DG model, allowing for the assessment of the factors influencing MNP dosimetry in vitro.
- Sedimentation behavior varied significantly based on particle size and type. Larger particles showed faster and more efficient sedimentation compared to smaller counterparts. PVC particles, for instance, reached near-complete deposition across both heights, with higher $f_{D \max}$ and AUC values for larger particles.

- Column height had a pronounced effect on smaller particles. Increasing the height led to reduced sedimentation efficiency for smaller MNPs, while larger particles were relatively unaffected, indicating the critical role of particle mass and Brownian motion in sedimentation dynamics.
- In the sensitivity analysis, hydrodynamic size, effective density, medium density, and viscosity are key parameters influencing sedimentation. Hydrodynamic size and effective density particularly enhance sedimentation, while higher medium density and viscosity generally hinder it. The adsorption dissociation constant appears to have minimal impact under the given condition.

These findings highlight the importance of considering both particle-specific properties (such as size and density) and medium characteristics (such as density and viscosity) when predicting MNP sedimentation in vitro. Understanding these factors will enhance the interpretation of MNP dosimetry, ultimately improving the reliability of in vitro toxicity studies for assessing potential health risks.

5 APPENDIX

Table S1 Predicted sedimentation metrics for PVCs at 3 mm and 6.6 mm column heights (iPSCs medium with 2% FBS)

MNPs	T_{max} (h)		$f_{D\ max}$ (%)		AUC (%*h)	
	3 mm	6.6 mm	3 mm	6.6 mm	3 mm	6.6 mm
PVC<1	9.0	16.5	96.5	96.5	4511.8	4400.7
PVC1-5	6.5	13.0a	97.4	97.4	4572.8	4482.9
PVC5-10	7.5	14.5	96.9	96.9	4584.9	4480.4

Figure S1. Predicted sedimentation in volume column height of 3 mm (iPSCs medium with 2% FBS).

PA<1 No SLS data available

Legend: Y-axis: fraction deposited (%); X-axis time in hours (48 hours)

Figure S2. Predicted sedimentation in volume column height of 6.6 mm (iPSCs medium with 2% FBS).

PA<1 No SLS data available

Legend: Y-axis: fraction deposited (%); X-axis time in hours (48 hours)

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